

SAUDI ARABIA AND CHINA RELATIONS

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The first relations between Arab countries and the People's Republic of China were established at the Bandung Conference in Indonesia in 1955. The cooling of China's relations with the Soviet Union led to the thawing of the ice between China and Saudi Arabia. In the 1973 Arab-Israeli War, Western countries and the United States sided with Israel, while China sided with the Arab countries. Oil-exporting Arab countries, led by Saudi Arabia, imposed an embargo on the sale of oil to countries that supported Israel in this war, which caused great concern in Western countries. China, which grew economically with the economic reform and foreign expansion policy initiated by Deng Xiaoping in 1978, became an oil importer in 1993 due to its increasing energy demand. Saudi Arabia's pro-Western policy made it reluctant to establish relations with Beijing, unlike other Arab countries that had established relations with China in various fields. The coldness between China and the USSR and the emergence of warm relations with the United States, and a number of measures taken by Beijing, prompted Riyadh to reconsider its relations with Beijing. As a result, Saudi Arabia established consular relations between China and Saudi Arabia in early 1990, and embassy relations in July.

Keywords: Republic of China, Saudi Arabia, relations, oil, United States.

After the Second World War, two hegemonic powers determined the direction of the world. These states fought to secure their interests in energy sources, including oil-rich Arab countries. When establishing their domestic policy, each Arab country preferred to familiarize itself with the development models of foreign states and tried to adapt these systems to local characteristics. During the period when both peace systems existed, the focus was on the development direction of the Arab Eastern countries towards the East or the West. Republic-type states mainly took the East, while monarchical states took the West. In this sense, during the period we are talking about, Arab countries established relations with China in accordance with their political systems. For example, while Egypt chose a socialist path which was interested in developing relations with China, Saudi Arabia, a Western-oriented monarchical state, avoided relations with China. The formation of the foreign policy of each state was influenced by various factors, including the real geopolitical situation in the world.

In fact, the first relations between Arab countries and the People's Republic of China were established during the Bandung Conference in Indonesia in 1955. Egyptian President G.A. Nasser asked the Chinese representative at the Bandung Conference to introduce him to the Soviet Union. The PRC's announcement of the "Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence" during the conference decisively changed the minds of the participants (30% of the participants were from Arab countries). [12, p.511] At this conference, Egyptian President G.A. Nasser had the opportunity to meet with Mao Zedong. Egypt pursued a socialist path in both its domestic and foreign policies. The upward trend in relations with the USSR during G.A. Nasser's time prompted Egypt to establish diplomatic relations with socialist China in 1956.

However, the gradual cooling of China's relations with the Soviet Union led to the thawing of the ice between China and Saudi Arabia. In the 1973 Arab-Israeli War, Western countries and the United States sided

with Israel, while China sided with the Arab countries. The embargo imposed by oil-exporting Arab countries, led by Saudi Arabia, on the sale of oil to countries that defended Israel in this war caused great concern in Western countries. China, on the other hand, supported the decision of the Oil Embargo implemented under the leadership of Saudi Arabia.

The policy pursued by Mao Zedong under the name of the "cultural revolution" led to the destruction of a number of Chinese intellectuals and the decline of the country. In October 1976, the Chinese Communist Party, with the support of the broad masses of the people, crushed the counter-revolutionary group of Lin Biao and Jiang Qin.[3, p.67] Deng Xiaoping, who played an important role in China's economic development, was removed from all his posts as a result of Mao Zedong's wrong policies. Deng Xiaoping showed the damage that Mao Zedong's "Cultural Revolution" had done to the economy, science and education and fought against his policies. After Mao Zedong's death in 1976 and the arrest of the "Gang of Four", the situation in the country changed. In July 1977, at the request of the whole country, Deng Xiaoping was reinstated to all the party and state posts from which he had been removed during the "Cultural Revolution".[3, p.67] Under Deng Xiaoping's leadership, the reforms carried out in the political and economic system, including the modernization of the country and the development of the national economy, have ensured the development of China and made it one of the leading countries. China, which has been growing economically with the economic reform and foreign expansion policy initiated by Deng Xiaoping in 1978, has become an oil-importing country since 1993 due to its increasing energy demand.

Deng Xiaoping came to power after the death of Mao Zedong in 1976. With his coming to power, he laid the foundation for a new stage in the country's development. The economic reforms he carried out, and especially the "Open Door Policy" in 1978, ensured the rapid development of China. China's economic development increased the country's dependence on energy

sources. Thanks to the "Open Door Policy", a free market economy based on central planning was successful as the original model tested for the first time in a large, populous, developing country like China. [1, p.7] Since 1990, China has started energy diplomacy. Confidently moving in this direction, China has become the largest buyer of oil from Arab countries. China, which is in an alliance with Russia, is trying to play an important role in their political life in addition to trade relations. After the political processes that took place in Syria after the "Arab Spring", China, along with Russia and Iran, closely participated in the protection of the Bashar al-Assad regime. China implements its policy in the Middle East cautiously and in a balancing manner. Relations with Saudi Arabia and Iran, which are enemies of each other, are developing on an upward trajectory. Saudi Arabia, which pursues a Western-oriented policy, was reluctant to establish relations with Beijing, unlike other Arab countries that established relations with China in various fields. Until 1990, all Arab countries, except Bahrain, had established relations with China in various fields. Thus, the US influence is strong in the Gulf countries - Kuwait in 1966, Oman, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Bahrain - which gained independence in 1971. However, as a result of China's diplomatic efforts, Kuwait in 1971, Oman in 1978, the United Arab Emirates in 1984, Qatar in 1988, and the dwarf Arab country Bahrain established diplomatic relations with China in 1996. Saudi-Chinese relations witnessed positive developments starting with the restoration of relations between the two countries in 1990, and then Saudi-Chinese mutual relations increased at the presidential and other official levels. [13] Saudi Arabia implements its foreign policy within the Middle East subregion through the Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Persian Gulf, established in 1981. [9, p.33]

Relations between the People's Republic of China and the Soviet Union cooled. After US President Nixon's visit to Beijing in 1972, relations between the US and China were developing in a positive direction and they began to pursue common policies in a number of areas. The cooling between China and the USSR, the establishment of warm relations with the US, and a number of measures taken by Beijing prompted Riyadh to reconsider relations with Beijing. As a result, Saudi Arabia established consular relations between China and Saudi Arabia in early 1990, and embassy relations in July. [12, p.53] Although China joined the struggle for the Middle East late, it is successfully moving on this path. China is one of the world's greatest powers today. China's growing demand for energy has led it to develop relations with Arab countries, especially Saudi Arabia, and the Gulf countries.

Military cooperation between Saudi Arabia and China began earlier than diplomatic relations. Relations between Beijing and Riyadh began to intensify with military cooperation in the 1980s, after China supplied Saudi Arabia with a part of CSS-2(DF-3) medium-range ballistic missiles. [12, p.54] Since this period, business relations between China and Saudi Arabia have begun to develop.

Since China is interested in developing relations with Saudi Arabia, in 1981 it allowed Muslims living in its country to go on the Hajj pilgrimage, began publishing the Quran, and allocated funds for the repair and maintenance of mosques. These and other measures also played an important role in the rapprochement of the two countries. In December 1982, Saudi Arabia's Foreign Minister Prince Saud al-Faisal visited China and held talks with his Chinese counterpart. [12, p.54] From the last years of Mao Zedong's rule until 1989, both the United States and the People's Republic of China were trying to reduce Soviet influence in the Middle East and were actively involved in this area. The examples given show that these countries were acting in their national interests. Since the 2000s, there has been a rapprochement between Russia and China, and both countries have pursued a common policy in Iran and Syria.

China was one of the first countries to recognize the Palestine Liberation Organization and provided large amounts of financial assistance to this country. It defended the Arab position in the 1973 war. According to 2018 data, China, which has a trade turnover of \$200 billion with Arab countries, plans to import \$8 trillion from Arab countries in the next five years. [1, p.8] China, which has three important economic weapons: investment, foreign trade and aid, is the largest customer of Middle Eastern oil. [1, p.9] It is the largest foreign investor in Iran. Unlike the United States, China does not interfere in the internal affairs of Arab countries, does not threaten their sovereignty and integrity, does not finance any radical organizations, and prefers cooperation and mutual benefit.

China's active implementation of the "One Belt, One Road" project provides the basis for the emergence of the United States as a competitor in the Middle East. Geopolitical stability and security in the region are extremely important for China. The creation of a security system by the United States in the Gulf facilitates the establishment of trade relations both for these monarchies and for countries that invest in these countries and import oil and gas. It is no coincidence that US President Carter stated in an interview on January 23, 1980 that he would consider any intervention to seize control of the Persian Gulf as an attack on the vital interests of the United States and would use all means, including weapons, to repel this attack. [7, p.433-434] The United States has nearly 65 thousand soldiers in permanent bases in the region. With the end of the Cold War, new shades began to emerge in international relations. China's open condemnation of the Soviet intervention in Afghanistan was one of the factors that led to its rapprochement with the United States, which shared the same opinion. "Currently, the oil-exporting states of the Persian Gulf, which need political stability and a reliable consumer, are also inclined to China. Thus, unlike the United States, the PRC considers stability more important than democracy and demonstrates that it is a reliable partner." [10, p.45] The three main oil suppliers to the Chinese economy are OPEC members Saudi Arabia, Angola, and Iran. [10, p.69] Many experts call China's policy "deterrence diplomacy" or "soft and silent"

policy. The essence of "deterrence diplomacy" is to increase the political influence of its country in the region, not to interfere in the internal affairs of any country and not to interfere with countries that have influence in the region. This policy satisfies the Gulf countries. Saudi Arabia is the country that the PRC attaches the most importance to after Egypt. The relative stability in Saudi Arabia compared to Arab countries such as Syria, Lebanon, Iraq, Yemen, and Libya is of great importance to the PRC. For example, China's \$ 18.5 billion investment in Libya was lost after the overthrow of Muammar Gaddafi. However, the transition to a market economy within the framework of socialism, the creation of free economic zones, in short, ensuring the parallel operation of an economic system that encompasses two opposite poles, gave positive results in the country in a short time. [10, p.13] The views of the famous political scientist Z. Brzezinski, who analyzed China's position, attract attention. He writes: "The most correct foreign policy course for China is to spend its power economically, create conditions for future economic development, cautiously form an alliance of Asian countries and in the future involve Japan in this alliance." [10, p.160] No matter how cautious China pursues its policy, it is trying to use the tension between Riyadh and Washington as much as possible.

China's involvement in Saudi Arabia is becoming increasingly widespread. It has set itself the goal of using Saudi Arabia's natural resources to meet the growing needs of China's rapidly developing economy. Riyadh, which has high-quality oil reserves, had a strong position in OPEC. After Xi Jinping (or Tsjinpin) came to power on March 14, 2013, a new era began in relations between China and the Gulf countries. Thus, since that year, China's foreign policy has been focused on implementing the "One Belt, One Road" (OBOR) strategy, which combines the "Great Silk Road Economic Belt" and the "21st Century Maritime Silk Road" projects. China's bi-policy has been successful, it can be said that the Arab world has almost joined OBOR, and a year later China presented the first project at the Arab Forum. The basis for military cooperation between Saudi Arabia and China was laid after the 1988 agreement, in which Saudi Arabia acquired Rih-Thara missiles (£882).[13] In November 1999, a meeting was held between Chinese President Jiang Zemin and the King of Saudi Arabia, which resulted in the signing of the Strategic Petroleum Cooperation Agreement.[5, p.308] With this agreement, Saudi Arabia opened its domestic market to Chinese investment and Beijing was allowed to operate in its oil fields.

In 2003, China's condemnation of the US intervention in Iraq increased Beijing's influence in the Arab world. The visit of Chinese President Hu Jintao to the Middle East in 2004 was a significant event in China's relations with Arab countries.[10, p. 165] The negotiations yielded positive results, and the establishment of the China-Arab Cooperation Forum was announced. In the same year, China's Torres Petrochemical Corporation won the tender for the development of a gas field in Saudi Arabia, beating out its American competitors.

In July 2004, six finance ministers of the Gulf Cooperation Council visited China and signed a "Framework Agreement on Economic, Investment and Technological Cooperation" with China.[5, p. 308] It is known that Japan has also established extensive economic relations with the Gulf countries to meet its energy needs in the Middle East. As a result of China's purposeful policy, it has surpassed Japan, taking second place after the United States in the international economy in the Middle East. China is the world's largest oil importer.

Both China and Saudi Arabia are interested in increasing trade. To this end, both sides are working to increase trade volume from \$5 billion in 2002 to \$16 billion in 2005 and \$20 billion in 2010. [5, p.309]

After achieving this goal, a plan is being prepared to increase trade volume again in the coming years.

In early 2016, Xi Jinping visited Saudi Arabia, the largest Gulf country. Of particular importance for the integration of the CEEC into Chinese economic initiatives, Xi Jinping visited Riyadh from January 19 to 23, 2016, as part of his Middle East tour, and the two sides signed a joint communiqué on comprehensive strategic partnership, as well as 15 cooperation agreements in various fields within the framework of the project. [11, p.3]

China has been supporting the Saudi-backed government in Yemen, not Iran, in its handling of the Houthis. This stems from Beijing's intention to build a military base in neighboring Djibouti. For China, this first overseas military base is a link in its "string of pearls" - a stronghold for its economic expansion from the South China Sea to North Africa. [11, p.6] The construction of this military infrastructure is also aimed at ensuring the security of oil supplies. Having opened its first overseas military base in Djibouti in 2017 (Djibouti also has a US base), China is determined to increase its military presence in the region. China, which competes most with the US on the seas, especially in the South China Sea, is expanding and modernizing not only its naval forces but also its merchant marine. [11, p.7] During Saudi Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman's visit to China in February 2019, several bilateral agreements were signed, including a \$10 billion deal to build an oil refining and petrochemical complex in China. In addition, a Saudi-Chinese investment conference was held, where 35 deals worth more than \$28 billion were signed. Overall, Chinese investment in Saudi Arabia increased by 100 percent in 2019. Saudi Arabia has become China's largest oil exporter and is also gaining influence in the region. The Persian Gulf as a whole is China's largest energy supplier. [2]

As a leader in the Muslim world as the "Custodian of the Two Holy Mosques," Saudi Arabia has been sympathetic to China's sensitivity and has ignored the persecution of Uyghur Muslims. Meanwhile, during his visit to China in February 2019, the Saudi Crown Prince justified Beijing's actions against the Uyghurs and expressed the view that "measures must be taken to protect national security." [8, p.4]

In addition, in July 2019, Saudi Arabia sent a letter of support to China to the United Nations, joining

thirty-seven countries praising it for its “remarkable achievements in the field of human rights.” [8, p.6]

The existence of conflicts, contradictions, and the instability of the military-political situation force China to stay on top of events in the Middle East and pursue a balancing policy. This policy of Beijing serves to strengthen its position in the Middle East. In March 2021, Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi paid a week-long visit to Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Oman, and Bahrain. In January 2022, foreign ministers of the Gulf monarchies, led by Saudi Arabia, visited China. Saudi Arabia is currently China's number one trading partner in the Middle East. [5, p.309]

Xi Jinping has called the Saudi kingdom “a great power in a multipolar world.” [4, p.1] It is clear that the development of constructive dialogue with Riyadh opens up vast opportunities for Beijing to promote friendly “Chinese power” in the Middle East and integrate the region into the OBOR project. [11, p.]

Trade between China and Saudi Arabia exceeded (80) billion dollars in 2021, and Chinese companies have invested more than (36) billion dollars in Saudi Arabia since 2005. [4, p.1] The project, which is expected to be commissioned in 2024, will be a 300,000-barrel-per-day oil refinery. [4, p.1]

Saudi Arabia is trying to maintain a balance between rival countries such as the United States and China. In 2022, Joe Biden visited Saudi Arabia. During his speech, he expressed the following idea: “We will not leave a vacuum for China, Russia or Iran to fill. The United States is not going anywhere.” [4, p. 2]

The Russo-Ukrainian war that began in 2022 has made Russia China's largest oil supplier. This has had a certain impact on China's oil imports from Saudi Arabia. In 2023, Russia surpassed Saudi Arabia as China's largest crude oil supplier for the first time since 2018, due to preferential Russian oil under OPEC and Saudi production cuts, capturing 19% of China's imports. [6, p. 7] This led to a decrease in Saudi Arabia's share of China's total crude oil imports from 17% to 15% in 2023 compared to 2022. At the same time, Russia's oil exports to China increased by 24% compared to the previous year, exceeding Saudi Arabia's exports by 2.14 million barrels, reaching a new peak. [6, p.7]

The PRC was persistent in expanding investment cooperation. To this end, an article titled “Let's Develop Our Thousand-Year Friendship and Create a Better Future Together” signed by Xi Jinping in the Saudi Arabian newspaper “Al-Riyadh” emphasizes that the two countries are working together for the prosperity of the world within the framework of “Vision 2030” and “In-Road-Belitiative”. [4, p.3] China has committed to building the first nuclear power plant in Saudi Arabia by 2022 and 15 more by 2032; the project cost was \$2.43 billion. [11, p. 3]

The successful reforms of Mohammed bin Salman have not only ensured the development of the country, but also have a positive impact on the global economy. Saudi Arabia plans the construction of the city of Neom

in a business zone with an area of 26.5 thousand square kilometers. The business zone will be located on the shores of the Gulf of Aqaba and the Red Sea, near the KSA borders with Jordan and Egypt. Among the investors that will participate in the construction of the city is China. Neom is expected to become the first city in the world where the number of robots will exceed the population and the GDP will reach \$100 billion by 2030

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